

Synthesis of 2-hydroxy-5-phenyazo Acetophenone

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ABSTRACT

Azo chemicals are crucial to the textile dye, and fiber industries. In the current investigation, certain azo compounds were produced in high yields by diazotizing a few substituted aromatic amines with concentrated HCl and NaNO₂, then coupling those products with 2-hydroxyacetophenone. The FTIR method was used to characterize the produced azo compounds

Keyword - Azo compounds, 2-hydroxy acetophenone, Aromatic amines.

1. INTRODUCTION

The azo dyes have variety of biological applications like antineoplastics, antidiabetics, antiseptics, anti-inflammatory and other useful chemotherapeutic agents.[1] Azo compounds are highly colored and have been used as dyes and pigments for a long time.[2] Azo dye compounds has great importance due to its environmental stability, electrical and optical properties.[3] The main advantage of azo dye is their cost effectiveness, which is due to the processes involved in manufacture.[4] The N=N group is called an azo or di-imide functional group and when found aromatic group in molecule this helps to stabilize the N=N group by making it a part of an extended delocalized system. This lead to making azo compounds colored and the molecules absorb the light in visible region.[5] Azo compounds are considered as class of organic colorants which consist of at least a conjugated chromophore azo (-N=N-) group in association with one or more aromatic or heterocyclic system.[6] The substituted azo compounds have the general structure R-N=N-R', where R and R' are alkyl, aryl or heterocyclic radicals. The azo dyes have been synthesized by the condensation of azo compounds with hydroxyl, aldehydes or ketones.[7] Some azo dye compounds shows biological activity against bacteria like digestive tract bacteria, Staphylococcus aureus etc.[8] The azo dyes compounds found to contain one or more azo groups(-N=N-) which are attached to carbon atom (SP² hybridized).[9] Synthesis of most azo compounds involves diazotization of a aromatic amine, followed by coupling amino and hydroxyl groups are commonly used for coupling reactions.[10]

In the present study, the azo dyes were synthesized by coupling 2-hydroxy acetophenone with benzene diazonium chloride and p-methyl diazonium chloride separately.

1.1 METHODS AND MATERIALS

Synthesis of 2-hydroxy-5-phenyazo acetophenone

The aryl diazonium chloride was prepared by dissolving pure aniline (0.93gm) with concentrated HCl (3ml) and water (3ml) and allow to cool at 5oC. in ice bath.NaNO₂ (0.69gm) was dissolved in water(10ml) at 5oC.The above two solutions were mixed with constant stirring. This mixture was added to the solution of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (1.36gm) which was dissolved in 10% NaOH solution at 5oC.The mixture were kept in ice bath with constant stirring for about 10min.The product precipitate was filtered and re-crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p.128oC.

2. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The azo compounds I and II had distinct melting points. By using IR spectra and qualitative functional group analysis, the synthesised azo compounds were identified.

2.1 hydroxy-5-phenyazo acetophenone

IR (KBr) cm^{-1}

The dye shows the absorption peak due to azo group, $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ stretching vibration at 1470cm^{-1} . Aromatic C-H stretching vibration bands appeared in the region of $2850-2940\text{cm}^{-1}$. aromatic C-H bending vibration bands appeared in the region of $845-730\text{cm}^{-1}$. $-\text{OH}$ stretching vibration bands appeared in the region of 3150cm^{-1} . $-\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration bands appeared in the region of 1620cm^{-1} . The decreased value of $-\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration may be attributed to the conjugation of the double bond.

There are functional groups such $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$, and $-\text{C}=\text{O}$, according to the qualitative functional group analysis..

3. CONCLUSIONS

It was decided to create azo dyes using the coupling agent 2-hydroxyacetophenone. The $\text{N}=\text{N}$ group is present in the produced compounds, making them suitable for use as dyes.

4. REFERENCES

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